

Pin-by-pin Simulation of PWR-Core by Using NECP-Bamboo3.0

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803510

ABSTRACT

Currently, the two-step core physics analysis method based on the homogenization concept still remains the mainstream approach for Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) core analysis. However, with the continuous advancement of nuclear energy technology, increasing attention has been paid to the pin-scale distributions of the core. The pin-by-pin method based on the pin-cell homogenization has thus emerged as the next-generation core physics analysis method, which also imposes higher requirements on both computational efficiency and accuracy. In 2025, the NECP Laboratory at Xi'an Jiaotong University (XJTU) published the pin-by-pin P_1 two-step calculation code system NECP-Bamboo3.0 for the PWR-core physics analysis. For neutronics calculation, compared with the widely used SP_3 calculation based on the transport correction approximation, the P_1 calculation adopted in NECP-Bamboo3.0 can achieve computational efficiency equivalent to diffusion calculation while accurately accounting for the anisotropic scattering effect, thus better balancing computational accuracy and efficiency. In addition, NECP-Bamboo3.0 was applied to the analysis of two commercial PWR cores, CNP650 and M310. Compared with the measurements regarding the startup physics tests and the depletion processes, the computational results of key core physical parameters all meet the corresponding engineering criteria. During the startup physics test, the error of the boron concentration is less than ± 25 ppm compared with the measured value, the moderator temperature coefficient error is less than ± 5 pcm·K⁻¹, the relative error of the control rod integral worth is less than $\pm 10\%$. During the burnup process, the critical boron concentration error is less than ± 30 ppm.

Keywords: Pin-by-pin, PWR, NECP-Bamboo3.0

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, there are mainly two main approaches for the neutronics calculation of Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) cores. The first one is the one-step method with fully detailed description including stochastic method such as the NECP-MCX[1], MCNP[2] and Serpent[3] codes and deterministic method such as the NECP-X[4], DeCART[5] and OpenMOC[6] codes. It can provide high accuracy and is expected to theoretically eliminate all approximations. However, the computational cost is too expensive even with the currently most advanced computing powers. Thus, it is often used to provide the reference solution. In contrast, approximations in spatial, neutron energy and angular spaces have been developed to provide efficient solution with acceptable accuracy. Among those, the most successful option is the two-step method based on homogenization. However, under the development of the next-generation reactors, the leakage and the heterogeneity of the core is stronger and stronger, more concerns on nuclear security and economic efficiency raise higher requirements to reactor core numerical simulation technology. Therefore, the legacy two-step method including assembly-homogenization approximation and pin-power reconstruction may not yield satisfactory results.

An alternative method with more detailed core modeling named pin-by-pin calculation is becoming attractive in recent years. It can increase the spatial resolution to pin scale and can directly obtain accurate pin-cell distribution with affordable computing cost. Different from the legacy two-step calculation, the heterogenous structure in each pin-cell is homogenized into a node instead of an entire

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fuel assembly in the first step. The whole-core pin-by-pin simulator eliminates the pin-power reconstruction and can provide a more accurate pin-power distribution. In addition, the multi-physics coupling in the whole-core calculation can also be refined into the pin-cell scale instead of the fuel assembly scale. It has to be noted that, due to the improvement of in spatial resolution, the number of neutron energy group should be refined from 2 to at least 4 or 7. Meanwhile, the legacy diffusion approximation will no longer be applicable mainly due to the approximation for the first-order scattering. At present, the SP₃ approximation is commonly employed mainly due to its compensation ability from two high-order angular flux moments. There have been several codes developed, such as AEGIS/SCOPE2[7] developed by Nagoya University and Nuclear Fuel Industries, DYN3D[8] developed by Helmholtz Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), PARCS[9] developed by Purdue University, HCMFD[10] developed by Korea Advanced Institute of Science Technology, SPHINCS[11] developed by Seoul National University.

NECP-Bamboo is independently developed by the NECP Laboratory of Xi'an Jiaotong University. Currently, it includes two versions: NECP-Bamboo1.0, which adopts the two-step method with nodal diffusion, and NECP-Bamboo2.0, which features the two-step method with pin-by-pin SP₃. Verified by the measured data of over 300 reactor-years from more than ten commercial PWRs, this software demonstrates stable and reliable numerical performance.

In the SP₃ approximation, 2 coupled diffusion-like equations have to be solved iteratively, which cost at least twice computing efforts compared with diffusion theory. It is urgent to develop a more efficient methodology that can theoretically reduce computational cost and improve computational efficiency. Considering the limitations of spatial mesh and the number of energy groups, many researches have attempted to further simplify SP₃ into diffusion approximation. However, the numerical results indicate that the pin-by-pin analysis based on the diffusion approximation have significant deviations, and the deviations of the pin-power will exceed industrial limits.

Under this circumstance, a pin-by-pin calculation methodology based on the P₁ approximation was proposed. The P₁ equation can be obtained by expanding the neutron angular flux into a first-order spherical harmonic function and integrates the angular flux in the angular phase space. It naturally considers the anisotropic scattering effect, which has higher accuracy compared to the diffusion equation and can achieve accuracy comparable to SP₃ equations. In addition, the equation form of the P₁ equation is also a diffusion-like equation, indicating that the required computational cost is basically the same as the diffusion approximation.

In previous study[12], we proposed a pin-cell homogenization method for the P₁ equation and its finite difference solution, and verified the correctness using several relatively simple calculation problems. Based on the theoretical model, the corresponding software NECP-Bamboo3.0 has been developed. This paper provides a brief introduction to the NECP-Bamboo3.0, with the focus on demonstrating its practical effects, in physics analysis of commercial PWR-cores.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL

2.1. Pin-cell homogenization for P₁ equation

The multi-group P₁ equation is shown as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \nabla J_g(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{t,g}(\mathbf{r})\Phi_g(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{g'}^G \Sigma_{s0,g' \rightarrow g}(\mathbf{r})\Phi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) + \frac{\chi_g(\mathbf{r})}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^N \nu \Sigma_{f,g'}(\mathbf{r})\Phi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \\ \frac{1}{3} \nabla \Phi_g(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{t,g} \mathbf{J}_g(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s1,g' \rightarrow g} \mathbf{J}_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In order to numerically solve the equation above, define the diffusion coefficient matrix as follows:

$$\mathbf{D} = \frac{1}{3} (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_t - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s1})^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Then, the equation (1) can be transformed as:

$$-\nabla^2 \sum_{g'=1}^G D_{g,g} \phi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{t,g}(\mathbf{r}) \phi_g(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{g'}^G \Sigma_{s,0,g' \rightarrow g}(\mathbf{r}) \phi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) + \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \chi_g(\mathbf{r}) \sum_{g'=1}^N \nu \Sigma_{f,g'}(\mathbf{r}) \phi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (3)$$

The calculation equations for the homogenized cross-sections required to solve the P₁ equation are as follows:

$$\Sigma_{s1,u,gg'}^{\text{hom}} = \frac{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \int_{4\pi} \Omega_u \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega' \rightarrow \Omega) \phi_g^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega') d\Omega' d\Omega dV}{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \Omega_u \phi_g^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega dV} \quad (4)$$

$$\Sigma_{t,u,g}^{\text{hom}} = \frac{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \Omega_u \Sigma_{t,g}^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}) \phi_g^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega dV}{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \Omega_u \phi_g^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega dV} \quad (5)$$

$$\chi_g^{\text{hom}} \nu \Sigma_{f,g'}^{\text{hom}} = \frac{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \chi_g(\mathbf{r}) \nu \Sigma_{f,g'}^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}) \phi_{g'}^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega') d\Omega' dV}{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \phi_{g'}^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega dV} \quad (6)$$

$$\Sigma_{s0,gg'}^{\text{hom}} = \frac{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \int_{4\pi} \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega' \rightarrow \Omega) \phi_{g'}^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega') d\Omega' d\Omega dV}{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \phi_{g'}^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega dV} \quad (7)$$

$$\Sigma_{t,g}^{\text{hom}} = \frac{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \Sigma_{t,g}^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}) \phi_g^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega dV}{\int_V \int_{4\pi} \phi_g^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega dV} \quad (8)$$

By substituting equations (4) and (5) into equation (2), the homogenized diffusion coefficient matrix can be obtained. In addition, to ensure the leakage conversion, PDFs are introduced, among which the calculation equation for the homogenized neutron surface flux is as follows:

$$\phi^{\text{hom, Sur}} = \frac{1}{A_{\perp s} \Delta h_s} \int_V \int_{4\pi} \phi_g^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega dV - \frac{\Delta h_s}{2A_{\perp s}} \left(\overline{D}^{\text{hom}} \right)^{-1} \int_{\Gamma_i} \int_{4\pi} \langle \mathbf{n}_s, \Omega \rangle \phi^{\text{het}}(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega ds \quad (9)$$

2.2. The finite difference method for the P₁ equation

In this work, the central Finite Difference Method (FDM) was employed to discretize and numerically solve the P₁ equation. Please refer to the Ref [12] for detailed derivation process. For convenience, transfer the equation into vector form. Taking the x-direction as an example, the leakage item turns out to be:

$$L_x = \frac{2}{\Delta x_i} \frac{D_{i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} [-\phi_i(x_{i-1/2}, y_j, z_k) + 2\phi_{i,j,k} - \phi_i(x_{i+1/2}, y_j, z_k)] \quad (10)$$

By introducing the boundary condition with discontinuity factors

$$\mathbf{f}_{i,j,k}^E \phi_{i,j,k}(x_{i+1/2}, y_j, z_k) = \mathbf{f}_{i+1,j,k}^W \phi_{i+1,j,k}(x_{i+1/2}, y_j, z_k) \quad (11)$$

and the half-node linear (HNL) approximation:

$$\mathbf{D}_x(x_i, y_j, z_k) \frac{\phi_{i,j,k}(x_{i+1/2}, y_j, z_k) - \phi_{i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i / 2} = \mathbf{D}_x(x_{i+1}, y_j, z_k) \frac{\phi_{i+1,j,k} - \phi_{i+1,j,k}(x_{i+1/2}, y_j, z_k)}{\Delta x_{i+1} / 2} \quad (12)$$

the surface flux can be obtained by simultaneously solving the Eqs (11) and (12):

$$\phi_{i,j,k}(x_{i+1/2}, y_j, z_k) = \left(\frac{D_{x,i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} + \frac{f_{i,j,k}^E}{f_{i+1,j,k}^W} \frac{D_{x,i+1,j,k}}{\Delta x_{i+1}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{D_{x,i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} \phi_{i,j,k} + \frac{D_{x,i+1,j,k}}{\Delta x_{i+1}} \phi_{i+1,j,k} \right) \quad (13)$$

$$\phi_{i+1,j,k}(x_{i+1/2}, y_j, z_k) = \left(\frac{f_{i,j,k}^W}{f_{i-1,j,k}^E} \frac{D_{x,i-1,j,k}}{\Delta x_{i-1}} + \frac{D_{x,i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{D_{x,i-1,j,k}}{\Delta x_{i-1}} \phi_{i-1,j,k} + \frac{D_{x,i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} \phi_{i,j,k} \right) \quad (14)$$

Replacing i with $i-1$ in Eq. (14), substituting it and Eq. (13) into Eq. (10), the leakage in x -direction can be obtained:

$$L_x = \frac{2}{\Delta x_i} \frac{D_{x,i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} \left[\phi_{i,j,k} - \left(\frac{D_{x,i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} + \frac{f_{i,j,k}^E}{f_{i+1,j,k}^W} \frac{D_{x,i+1,j,k}}{\Delta x_{i+1}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{D_{x,i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} \phi_{i,j,k} + \frac{D_{x,i+1,j,k}}{\Delta x_{i+1}} \phi_{i+1,j,k} \right) - \left(\frac{f_{i,j,k}^W}{f_{i-1,j,k}^E} \frac{D_{x,i-1,j,k}}{\Delta x_{i-1}} + \frac{D_{x,i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{D_{x,i-1,j,k}}{\Delta x_{i-1}} \phi_{i-1,j,k} + \frac{D_{x,i,j,k}}{\Delta x_i} \phi_{i,j,k} \right) + \phi_{i,j,k} \right] \quad (15)$$

Similarly, the leakages in y and z directions can also be obtained similarly. With those leakages, the discretized P_1 equation could become the following form

$$\sum_{x,y,z} L + \sum_{r,i,j,k} \phi_{r,i,j,k} = w_{i,j,k} \quad (16)$$

For those meshes at the boundaries, the approach is completely the same, with only slight differences in the leakage term, which will not be described in detail.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

To validate the program developed in this paper, the nodal diffusion code NECP-Bamboo1.0 is used for comparison in terms of both computational accuracy and efficiency. Specifically, NECP-Bamboo1.0 performs single-CPU calculation, while NECP-Bamboo3.0 employs 78-CPU's parallel computing.

3.1. M310

The M310 reactor adopts the technical scheme of a three-loop, 1000 MW(e) class PWR nuclear power plant. This plant has a planned service life of 40 years, with the core's nominal electrical power reaching 2895 MW and the operating pressure maintained at 15.5 MPa.

3.1.1. Startup physics tests

For the startup physics test, the calculation results of each key safety parameter are presented in the Table I - Table III. As can be seen from the table, all results meet the industrial limits (CBC: ± 50 ppm; MTC: ± 5 pcm \cdot K $^{-1}$; CR Worth: $\pm 10\%$). Additionally, NECP-Bamboo 3.0 achieves higher calculation accuracy, and the errors of nearly all its results are lower than those of the nodal diffusion two-step method.

Table I. Critical Boron Concentration.

Bank position	Nodal diffusion Error/ppm	NECP-Bamboo3.0 Error/ppm
ARO	-13	-15
Rin	-18	-14
R+G1in	-23	-13

Table II. Moderator Temperature Coefficient.

Bank position	Nodal diffusion Error/ pcm·K ⁻¹	NECP-Bamboo3.0 Error/ pcm·K ⁻¹
ARO	-0.75	0.41
Rin	-2.64	-1.78
R+G1in	-2.70	-1.76

Table III. Control Rod Worth.

Bank position	Nodal diffusion		NECP-Bamboo3.0	
	Error/pcm	Relative Error/%	Error/pcm	Relative Error/%
R	23	1.8	-12	-0.9
N1	13	1.3	-8	-0.8
N2	32	4.2	11	1.4
G1	-2	-0.4	-5	-1.3
G2	10	1.1	-9	-1.0
SA	4	3.8	4	3.8
SB	47	4.1	17	1.5
SC	16	2.4	-2	-0.3
SD	7	0.9	-1	-0.1

3.1.2. Depletion process

The boron dilution curve and its deviation for the first-cycle load follow are shown in Figure 1. The figure presents some measured points and the error between the calculated values and these measured points. Relative to the measured points, the error of the critical boron concentration (CBC) calculated by NECP-Bamboo3.0 $\leq \pm 25$ ppm, indicating good calculation accuracy. On the one hand, this error is far smaller than the CBC accuracy requirement in industrial operation. On the other hand, the stable error also shows that the calculation model can maintain good adaptability under different load conditions and different burnup stages. In addition, it can be seen from the figure that the error of the nodal diffusion two-step method increases in the later stage of the core life; in contrast, NECP-Bamboo 3.0 achieves higher accuracy. Regarding computational time, NECP-Bamboo1.0 takes an average of 416 seconds per burnup step, while NECP-Bamboo3.0 requires an average of 13.32 CPU-hours per burnup step. This is because NECP-Bamboo3.0 performs a 4-group pin-by-pin P_1 calculation, resulting in a solution vector length that is more than a thousand times longer than that of the nodal diffusion calculation used in NECP-Bamboo1.0.

3.2. CNP650

CNP650 is an improved and independently designed reactor in China based on M310. It has a core rated power of 1930 MW and an operating pressure of 15.5 MPa.

3.2.1. Startup physics tests

For the startup physics test, the calculation results of each key safety parameter are presented in the Table IV - Table VI. As can be seen from the table, all results meet the industrial limits. Additionally, NECP-Bamboo 3.0 achieves higher calculation accuracy, and the errors of nearly all its results are lower than those of the nodal diffusion two-step method.

3.2.2. Depletion process

The boron dilution curve and its deviation for the first-cycle load follow are shown in Figure 2. The figure presents some measured points and the deviation between the calculated values and these measured points. Compared with the measured points, the critical boron concentration (CBC) calculated by NECP-Bamboo 3.0 has a smaller error, which is always within ± 20 ppm. Regarding computational time, NECP-Bamboo1.0 takes an average of 223 seconds per burnup step, while NECP-Bamboo3.0 requires an average of 5.28 CPU-hours per burnup step.

Table IV. Critical Boron Concentration.

Bank position	Nodal diffusion Error/ppm	NECP-Bamboo3.0 Error/ppm
ARO	-16	4
Din	-18	-1
Cin	-15	1
Bin	-18	-7
Ain	-16	6

Figure 1. CBC error of M310

Table V. Moderator Temperature Coefficient.

Bank position	Nodal diffusion Error/ pcm · K ⁻¹	NECP-Bamboo3.0 Error/ pcm · K ⁻¹
Sin	-4.52	-4.12

Table VI. Control Rod Worth.

Bank position	Nodal diffusion		NECP-Bamboo3.0	
	Error/pcm	Relative Error/%	Error/pcm	Relative Error/%
D	17	4.7	-7	-0.7
C	66	7.6	48	5.5
S	20	1.3	-25	-1.5

3.2.3. Depletion process

The boron dilution curve and its deviation for the first-cycle load follow are shown in Figure 2. The figure presents some measured points and the deviation between the calculated values and these measured points. Compared with the measured points, the critical boron concentration (CBC) calculated by NECP-Bamboo 3.0 has a smaller error, which is always within ± 20 ppm.

Figure 2. CBC error of CNP650

4. CONCLUSIONS

To verify the correctness of NECP-Bamboo 3.0, this study applies it to different pressurized water reactor (PWR) problems. Two core scenarios—startup physics test calculation and load follow calculation—are used, with M310 and CNP650 reactors selected for simulation. The study also compares its calculation performance with that of the nodal diffusion two-step method.

Numerical results show that the calculation results of both methods can meet the constraints of commercial PWR core nuclear design. On this basis, NECP-Bamboo 3.0 demonstrates significantly higher accuracy than the nodal diffusion two-step method, further illustrating the accuracy advantage of the pin-scale two-step method.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No.12575186).

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